

Supplementary Material S1. List of cecidomyiid species in the Brazilian biomes, including their feeding habit, and associated host plant or prey recorded in the original description or inventories in Brazil. Type locality is indicated as “original description”; otherwise, the localities are from inventories. Abbreviation: NA: not applicable, NI: not informed.

Diptera species	Biome	Feeding habit	Host plant/Prey	Sites
<i>Alexomyia ciliata</i> Felt, 1921	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	NI	PA (undetermined, original description)
<i>Alycaulus globulus</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim, original description), Rio de Janeiro (Grumari, Itatiaia, Rio das Ostras); SP (Bertioga); ES (Santa Teresa); MG (Viçosa)
<i>Alycaulus hexadentatus</i> Urso-Guimarães, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Smilacaceae	SP (Altinópolis, original description)
<i>Alycaulus mikaniae</i> Rübbsaamen, 1915	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	AM (undetermined, original description)
<i>Alycaulus trilobata</i> Möhn, 1964	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	SP (Bertioga, original description)
<i>Anadiplosis caetetensis</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest, Caatinga	gall inducer	Fabaceae	BA (Caeteté, original description)
<i>Anadiplosis procera</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	BA (Itaparica, original description)
<i>Anadiplosis pulchra</i> Tavares, 1916	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Anadiplosis venusta</i> Tavares, 1916	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Anasphondylia myrtacea</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Andirodiplosis bahiensis</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	BA (Salvador, original description); SP (Luiz Antônio)
<i>Anisodiplosis waltheriae</i> Maia, 2005	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Sterculiaceae	MG (Aimorés, original description), MT (Chapada dos Guimarães)
<i>Aphidoletes aphidimyza</i> (Rondani, 1847)	NI	predator	Aphididae (Hemiptera)	Brazil (undetermined, original description)

<i>Apodiplosis praecox</i> Tavares, 1922	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Arcivena kielmeyerae</i> Gagné, 1984	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Calophyllaceae	SP (Mogi Guaçu, original description)
<i>Arrabiadaeamyia serrata</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Bignoniaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Mangaratiba, São João da Barra)
<i>Asphondylia bahiensis</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Asphondylia borrieriae</i> Rübsaamen, 1905	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Caatinga, Cerrado	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	RJ (Arpoador/ Rio de Janeiro (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Mangaratiba, Maricá, Saquarema)
<i>Asphondylia canastrae</i> Urso-Guimarães & Amorim, 2002	Cerrado	gall inducer	Lamiaceae	MG (Delfinópolis, original description)
<i>Asphondylia cipo</i> Urso-Guimarães, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Santana do Riacho, original description)
<i>Asphondylia communis</i> Maia & Couri, 1992	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Olacaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, São João da Barra, Mangaratiba)
<i>Asphondylia cordiae</i> Möhn, 1959	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Boraginaceae	ES (Anchieta, Piúma); RJ (Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Carapebus, Campos de Goitacazes, Maricá, Quissamã, Rio de Janeiro, São João da Barra, Saquarema); SP (Bertioga, Ubatuba); RS (Porto Alegre)
<i>Asphondylia fructicola</i> Maia, 2009	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Solanaceae	AM (Porto Trombetas/Oriximiná, original description)
<i>Asphondylia glomeratae</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Rio de Janeiro (original description), Itatiaia, Valença); SP (Bertioga); ES (Santa Teresa); MG (Viçosa)
<i>Asphondylia gochnatiae</i> Maia, 2008	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Luz, original description)
<i>Asphondylia ingaiensis</i> Maia, 2021	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Ingaí, original description)
<i>Asphondylia maricensis</i> Maia & Couri, 1992	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Loranthaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)

<i>Asphondylia microcapillata</i> Maia, 2005	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MG (Três Marias, original description)
<i>Asphondylia moehni</i> Skuhrová, 1989	Atlantic Forest, Pampa	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RS (São Leopoldo (original description), Canela, Santa Tereza); ES (Santa Teresa); MG (Viçosa); RJ (Grumari); SP (Bertioga, Ubatuba)
<i>Asphondylia parva</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	BA (Madre de Deus, original description)
<i>Asphondylia peploniae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asclepiadaceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description)
<i>Asphondylia rochae</i> Tavares, 1918	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Onagraceae	CE (Fortaleza, original description)
<i>Asphondylia rufae</i> Maia, 2021	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MG (Dores do Indaiá, original description)
<i>Asphondylia sanctipetri</i> Urso-Guimarães & Amorim, 2002	Cerrado	gall inducer	Araliaceae	MG (Delfinópolis (original description), Aimorés); MT (Chapada dos Guimarães); SP (Ribeirão Preto)
<i>Asphondylia sennae</i> Maia & Couri, 1992	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Asphondylia serrata</i> Maia, 2004	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Tiradentes, original description)
<i>Asphondylia stachytarpheta</i> Barnes, 1932	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	RJ (Mangaratiba, original description)
<i>Asphondylia struthanthi</i> (Rübsaamen, 1915)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Loranthaceae	CE (Serra do Baturité, original description)
<i>Asphondylia sulphurea</i> Tavares, 1909	Pampa	gall inducer	Smilacaceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)
<i>Asphondylia tournefortiae</i> Rübsaamen, 1915	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Boraginaceae	AC (São Francisco on Acre river/Auristela, original description)
<i>Asphondylia ulei</i> Rübsaamen, 1908	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Palmeiras, original description)
<i>Asphondylia zeyheriae</i> Maia, 2021	Cerrado	gall inducer	Bignoniaceae	MG (Uberlândia and Serra do Cipó, both from original description)
<i>Asteromyia modesta</i> (Felt, 1907)	NI	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG and RJ (undetermined)

<i>Autodiplosis parva</i> Tavares, 1916	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Baccharomyia magna</i> Maia, 2012	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Ouro Preto, original description)
<i>Baccharomyia ramosina</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Brethesiamyia myrciae</i> Maia, 2009	Cerrado	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	MG (Três Marias, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia acaudata</i> Maia, 2004	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	ES (Santa Teresa); RJ (Maricá (original description), Angra dos Reis, Arraial do Cabo Carapebus, Mangaratiba, São Francisco de Itabapoana); BA (Porto Seguro)
<i>Bruggmannia braziliensis</i> Tavares, 1906	Pampa	gall inducer	Myrsinaceae	RS (São Leopoldo)
<i>Bruggmannia chapadensis</i> Proença & Maia, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia elongata</i> Maia & Couri, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Angra dos Reis, Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, São Francisco de Itabapoana, São João da Barra, Saquarema); BA (Porto Seguro); ES (Conceição da Barra, Guarapari); SP (Bertioga); RS (Canela), SC (Babitonga)
<i>Bruggmannia globulifex</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Serra dos Órgãos, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia lignicola</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Serra do Macaé, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia longicauda</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia longiseta</i> Kieffer, 1913	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	AM (Juruá, original description, Barcelos)

<i>Bruggmannia micrura</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	SC (undetermined, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia monteiroi</i> Maia & Couri, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia neeana</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Bruggmannia robusta</i> Maia & Couri, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	BA (Porto Seguro); ES (Santa Tereza, Conceição da Barra); RJ (Maricá (original description), Angra dos Reis, Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Mangaratiba, Rio das Ostras, São Francisco de Itabapoana, São João da Barra, Saquarema); SP (Bertioga); RS (Canela)
<i>Bruggmannia ruebsaameni</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	SC (Pedras Grandes, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella braziliensis</i> Tavares, 1909	Pampa	gall inducer	Moraceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella byrsonimae</i> (Maia & Couri, 1992)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description); BA (Caitité); ES (Santa Teresa)
<i>Bruggmanniella doliocarp</i> i Maia, 2010	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Dilleniaceae	MG (Dores do Indaiá, original description); DF (Planaltina); PE (Recife)
<i>Bruggmanniella duguetiae</i> Urso-Guimarães & Amorim, 2005	Cerrado	gall inducer	Annonaceae	SP (São Carlos, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella ingae</i> Urso-Guimarães & Amorim, 2005	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	SP (between São José do Rio Preto and Tapiratiba, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella maytenuse</i> (Maia & Couri, 1992)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Celastraceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), São Francisco de Itabapoana, São João da Barra)
<i>Bruggmanniella miconia</i> Garcia, Lamas	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	SP (Sorocaba, original description)

& Urso-Guimarães, 2020				
<i>Bruggmanniella miconiae</i> Carvalho-Fernandes, Maia & Rodrigues, 2020	Cerrado	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	MG (Dores do Indaiá, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella notatae</i> Rodrigues & Maia, 2020	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Lauraceae	RJ (Mangaratiba, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella oblita</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Anacardiaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Bruggmanniella sideroxyli</i> Rodrigues & Maia, 2020	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	RJ (Mangaratiba, original description)
<i>Brugmannia depressa</i> Kieffer, 1913	Atlantic Forest, Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	AC (Juruá Miri), AM (undetermined), MG (undetermined), PA (Belém), RJ (Floresta da Tijuca, Teresópolis) SC (undetermined) - all from the original description
<i>Bryocrypta alagoana</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	AL (Quebrangulo, original description)
<i>Bryocrypta matogrossensis</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	MT (Itiquira, original description)
<i>Burseramyia braziliensis</i> Maia & Fonseca, 2012	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	SP (Bertioga, original description); ES (Santa Teresa)
<i>Cassidoides japi</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	SP (Jundiaí, original description)
<i>Cassidoides oliveirae</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	GO (Mineiros, original description)
<i>Cerciplanus cipo</i> Garcia & Urso-Guimarães, 2020	Cerrado	gall inducer	Ochnaceae	MG (Santana do Riacho, original description)

<i>Cerciplanus tocantinensis</i> Garcia & Urso-Guimarães, 2020	Cerrado	gall inducer	Ochnaceae	TO (Araguaína, original description)
<i>Claspettomyia angelicae</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	AL (Quebrangulo, original description)
<i>Claspettomyia groverae</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	SP (Sertãozinho, original description); MS (Bodoquena, original description)
<i>Claspettomyia niheii</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	PI (Corrente, original description) and MS (Bodoquena, original description)
<i>Claspettomyia periotoi</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	SP (Teodoro Sampaio, original description); MS (Bodoquena, original description)
<i>Claspettomyia verasilvae</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	SP (Sertãozinho, original description)
<i>Cleitodiplosis graminis</i> (Tavares, 1916)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Poaceae	BA (undetermined, original description) and RJ (undetermined, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis agerati</i> Maia, 2016	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	MG (Dores do Indaiá)
<i>Clinodiplosis alternantherae</i> Gagné, 2004	NI	gall inducer	Asteraceae	Brazil (undetermined, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis bahiensis</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	BA (Madre de Deus, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis bellum</i> Urso-Guimarães & Carmo-Neto, 2015	Cerrado	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	SP (Altinópolis, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis cattleyae</i> Felt, 1908	NI	gall inducer	Orchidaceae	Brazil (undetermined, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis cearensis</i> (Tavares, 1917)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	CE (Fortaleza, original description)

<i>Clinodiplosis cecropiae</i> Proença & Maia, 2020	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Urticaceae	RO (Monte Negro, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis chlorophorae</i> Rübsaamen, 1905	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Moraceae	RJ (Fábrica, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis conica</i> Oliveira & Maia, 2008	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Carapebus, Mangaratiba)
<i>Clinodiplosis costai</i> Maia, 2005	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapindaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Carapebus, Mangaratiba)
<i>Clinodiplosis diodiae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Arraial do Cabo)
<i>Clinodiplosis eupatorii</i> (Felt, 1911a)	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	PA (undetermined, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis floricola</i> Novo-Guedes & Maia, 2008	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis iheringi</i> Tavares, 1925	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	SC (Joinville, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis marcetiae</i> (Tavares, 1917)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis maricaensis</i> Fernandes & Maia, 2011	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Erythroxylaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Carapebus, Mangaratiba)
<i>Clinodiplosis melissae</i> Maia, 1993a	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Lamiaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis profusa</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Cabo Frio, Arraial do Cabo, Grumari, Marambaia, Mangaratiba, São João da Barra, Saquarema)
<i>Clinodiplosis pulchra</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	BA (Madre de Deus, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis quartelensis</i> Maia & Oliveira 2019	Cerrado	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	MG (Quartel São João, original description)
<i>Clinodiplosis rubiae</i> (Tavares, 1918)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Clusiamyia granulosa</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Clusiaceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Casimiro de Abreu)

<i>Clusiamyia nitida</i> Maia, 1997	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Clusiaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo Macaé, Paraty, Quissamã, Silva Jardim)
<i>Compsodiplosis itaparicana</i> Tavares, 1922	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	undetermined	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Compsodiplosis luteoalbida</i> Tavares, 1909	Pampa	gall inducer	Smilacaceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)
<i>Contarinia gemmae</i> Maia, 2002	Atlantic Forest, Amazon Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Clusiaceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description); AM (Amanã); BA (Sebastião Laranjeiras); GO (Cavalcante, Pirenópolis, Teresina de Goiás); MG: (Januária, São Tomé das Letras); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Contarinia ubiquita</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim, original description)
<i>Contodiplosis friburgensis</i> (Tavares, 1915)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Styracaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Contodiplosis humilis</i> (Tavares, 1915)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Styracaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Contodiplosis tristis</i> (Tavares, 1915)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Styracaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Cordiamyia globosa</i> Maia, 1996	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Boraginaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Rio das Ostras, São João da Barra, São Francisco de Itabapoana, Saquarema); ES (Conceição da Barra, Guarapari, Itaúnas); SC (Babitonga); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Costadiplosis maricaensis</i> Viceconte & Maia, 2009	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Loranthaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description); BA (Porto Seguro)
<i>Couridiplosis vena</i> Maia, 2004	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	MG (Tiradentes, original description); BA (Ilhéus); ES (Santa Leopoldina); SP (Altinópolis)
<i>Dactylodiplosis heisteriae</i> Rübsaamen, 1915a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Olacaceae	AC (São Francisco on Acre river/Auristela, original description)

<i>Dactylodiplosis heptaphylli</i> Maia, 2004	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Burseraceae	BA (Conde, Caravelas); ES (Linhares, Guarapari); RJ (Carapebus (original description), Macaé, São João da Barra, São Francisco de Itabapoana); MG (São Tomé das Letras)
<i>Dactylodiplosis icicaribae</i> Maia, 2002	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Burseraceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Mangaratiba)
<i>Dactylodiplosis petibaurum</i> Maia, 2021	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Lauraceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description)
<i>Dasineura braziliensis</i> (Tavares, 1922)	Cerrado	gall inducer	Burseraceae	BA (undetermined, original description); MG (Carrancas); MT (Fazenda Palmeiras)
<i>Dasineura byrsonimae</i> Maia, 2010	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	RJ (Carapebus and Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Rio das Ostras, Saquarema, São João da Barra, São Francisco de Itabapoana); ES (Conceição da Barra)
<i>Dasineura copacabanensis</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Arraial do Cabo (original description), Araruama, Cabo Frio, Saquarema, São João da Barra)
<i>Dasineura couepiae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Chrysobalanaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio); ES (Guarapari, São Mateus); BA (Caravelas, Conde, Porto Seguro)
<i>Dasineura gigantea</i> Angelo & Maia, 1999	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	PR (Piraquara (original description), Curitiba, Pontal do Paraná); SC (Itapoá)
<i>Dasineura globosa</i> Maia, 1996	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Grumari, Marambaia, Mangaratiba, Saquarema, São João da Barra)
<i>Dasineura marginalis</i> Maia, 2005	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Macaé (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Mangaratiba, Saquarema,)
<i>Dasineura myrciariae</i> Maia, 1996	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Carapebus, Marambaia, São Francisco de Itabapoana); ES (Guarapari, Santa Teresa)
<i>Dasineura occulta</i> Pereira-Colavite & Urso-Guimarães, 2013	Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	SP (São Carlos, original description)

<i>Dasineura ovalifoliae</i> Fernandes & Maia, 2011	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Erythroxyloaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Grumari, Marambaia, Saquarema.); ES (Santa Teresa)
<i>Dasineura tavaresi</i> Maia, 1996	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Carapebus, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, São João da Barra)
<i>Diadiplosis abacaxii</i> Culik & Ventura, 2013a	Atlantic Forest	predator	Coccidae and Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Cachoeiro de Itapemirim, original description)
<i>Diadiplosis bellingeri</i> Culik & Ventura, 2012	Atlantic Forest	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Domingos Martins, original description)
<i>Diadiplosis coccidivora</i> (Felt, 1911b)	Atlantic Forest	predator	Eriococcidae and Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (undetermined, original description)
<i>Diadiplosis floridana</i> (Felt, 1915a)	Atlantic Forest	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Domingos Martins, Sooretama, Cachoeiro de Itapemirim)
<i>Diadiplosis jamboi</i> Culik & Ventura, 2013b	Atlantic Forest	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Vitória, original description)
<i>Diadiplosis martinsensis</i> Culik & Ventura, 2013b	Atlantic Forest	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Domingos Martins, original description)
<i>Diadiplosis multifila</i> (Felt, 1907b)	Atlantic Forest	predator	Margarodidae, Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Vitória)
<i>Diadiplosis pseudococci</i> Felt, 1921b	NI	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	Brazil (undetermined)
<i>Diadiplosis saccharum</i> Urso-Guimarães, 2020	Cerrado	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	SP (Jaboticabal (original description), São Carlos)
<i>Diadiplosis vaupedis</i> (Harris, 1968)	Atlantic Forest	predator	Pseudococcidae (Hemiptera)	ES (Domingos Martins)
<i>Dialeria styracis</i> Tavares, 1918	Atlantic Forest, Caatinga	predator	Styracaceae	BA (Caeteté, original description)
<i>Dichodiplosis triangularis</i> (Felt, 1908)	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	BA (Salvador, original description)

<i>Didactylomyia longimana</i> (Felt, 1908)	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	MS (Aquidauana)
<i>Distinctamyia matogrossensis</i> Proença & Maia, 2021	Cerrado	gall inducer	Simarubaceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães, original description)
<i>Elachypalpus psidii</i> Maia & Nava, 2011	Pampa	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RS (Pelotas, original description)
<i>Epihormomyia miconiae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description); ES (Santa Teresa)
<i>Eugeniomyia dispar</i> Maia, Mendonça & Romanowski, 1997	Pampa	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RS (Pelotas, original description)
<i>Eugeniomyia triangularis</i> Maia & Nava, 2011	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Feltiella curtistylus</i> Gagné, 1984	Caatinga	predator	Tetranychidae (Acari)	PE (Petrolina, original description)
<i>Fernandesia meridionalis</i> Rodrigues & Maia, 2013	Pampa	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RS (São Francisco de Paula, original description)
<i>Frauenfeldiella coussapoe</i> Rübsaamen, 1905	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Moraceae	AC (Juruá Mirim, original description)
<i>Geraldiesia eupatorii</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Gnesiodiplosis itaparicae</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Rubiaceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Guareamyia purpura</i> Maia, 2007	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Meliaceae	SP (Bertioga, original description)
<i>Guarephila albida</i> Tavares, 1909	Pampa	gall inducer	Meliaceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)
<i>Haplopalpus serjaneae</i> Rübsaamen, 1915a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Sapindaceae	AC (Auristela, original description)
<i>Haplusia braziliensis</i> (Felt, 1915b)	Amazon Forest	fungivorous	NA	PA (Igarapé Açu, original description)
<i>Haplusia plumipes</i> Karsch, 1877	NI	fungivorous	NA	BA (undetermined, original description)

<i>Houardodiplosis rochae</i> Tavares, 1925	Amazon Forest, Caatinga	gall inducer	Combretaceae	CE (Fortaleza, original description)
<i>Insulestremia amenti</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2021	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	SP (Ibitinga, original description)
<i>Insulestremia amorimi</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2021	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	SP (Ribeirão Preto (original description), Sertãozinho, Teodoro Sampaio, São Carlos); MS (Bodoquena)
<i>Insulestremia sinclairi</i> Jaschhof, 2001	Amazon Forest, Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	MA (Bodoquena); RO (Porto Velho)
<i>Jatrophobia brasiliensis</i> Rübsaamen, 1908	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	AM (Fortaleza, Juruá Mirim); RJ (Mauá, Palmeiras, São Francisco do Itabapoana); SP (Bertioga); SC (Tubarão) – all in the original description
<i>Jorgenseniella eugeniae</i> Maia, 2005	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Arraial do Cabo, original description)
<i>Lestodiplosis braziliensis</i> (Tavares, 1920b)	Atlantic Forest	predator	NA	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Lestodiplosis floricola</i> (Rodrigues & Maia, 2010a)	Atlantic Forest	predator	Convolvulaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Lestodiplosis maricaensis</i> Santos & Maia, 2009	Atlantic Forest	predator	Fabaceae	RJ (Mangaratiba and Carapebus, original description)
<i>Lioidiplosis conica</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Tijuca/Rio de Janeiro (original description), Angra dos Reis, Grumari, Silva Jardim, Rio das Ostras, Valença); SP (Bertioga); RS (Canela)
<i>Lioidiplosis cylindrica</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim (original description), Angra dos Reis, Itatiaia, Mangaratiba, Paraty, Valença); MG (Viçosa); SP (Bertioga); SC (Babitonga); RS: (Canela)
<i>Lioidiplosis spherica</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim (original description), Angra dos Reis, Itatiaia, Mangaratiba, Paraty, Valença); MG (Viçosa); SP (Bertioga); RS (Canela)

<i>Lopesia aldinae</i> Fernandes & Maia, 2010	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	AM (Manaus, original description)
<i>Lopesia andirae</i> Garcia, Lima, Calado & Urso-Guimarães, 2017	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães); BA (Barreiras); SP (Luiz Antônio) – all in the original description
<i>Lopesia bilobata</i> Maia, 2004	Cerrado	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	MG (Tiradentes, original description)
<i>Lopesia brasiliensis</i> Rübsaamen, 1908	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	RJ (Fábrica, original description)
<i>Lopesia caulinaris</i> Maia, 2003	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Calophyllaceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Angra dos Reis); AM (Amanã); BA (São Sebastião); GO (Pirenópolis, Cavalcante); SC (Babitonga); MG (Januária, São Tomé das Letras); SP (Bertioga);
<i>Lopesia chapadensis</i> Garcia & Urso- Guimarães, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães, original description)
<i>Lopesia conspicua</i> Maia, 2002	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado, Caatinga	gall inducer	Calophyllaceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description); AM (Amanã); Bahia (Sebastião Laranjeiras); GO (Pirenópolis); MG (São Tomé das Letras, Januária); RN (Canguaretama); SC (São Francisco do Sul); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Lopesia davillae</i> Maia & Monteiro, 2017	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Dilleniaceae	RJ (Teresópolis, original description)
<i>Lopesia eichhorniae</i> Urso-Guimarães, 2014	Cerrado	gall inducer	Pontederiaceae	SP (Luiz Antônio, original description)
<i>Lopesia elliptica</i> Maia, 2003	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado, Caatinga	gall inducer	Calophyllaceae	RJ (Carapebus, original description); AM (Amanã); Bahia (Sebastião Laranjeiras); PA (Moju); PE (Rio Preto); RN (Canguaretama); GO (Pirenópolis); MG (São Tomé das Letras); MT (Santa Terezinha); SC (Babitonga); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Lopesia erythroxyli</i> Rodrigues & Maia, 2010	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Erythroxylaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Angra dos Reis, Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Grumari, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Saquarema, São

<i>Lopesia grandis</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	João da Barra); ES (Santa Teresa); SP (Itanhaém) PB (Mataraca); BA (Belmonte, Camamu, Ilhéus, Itacaré, Nova Viçosa, Porto Seguro, Santa Cruz de Cabrália, Uma, Valença); ES (Aracruz, Conceição da Barra, Guarapari; Presidente Kennedy, São Mateus); RJ (Carapebus (original description), Angra dos Reis, Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Maricá, Paraty, São Francisco de Itabapoana; SP (Bertioga, Cananeia, Ubatuba); SC (Babitonga)
<i>Lopesia indaiensis</i> Maia & Oliveira, 2018	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MG (Dores do Indaiá, original description); PE (Tamandaré); RJ (Mangaratiba); SP (Bertioga); SP (Bertioga, original description)
<i>Lopesia leandrae</i> Maia, 2019	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	
<i>Lopesia linearis</i> Maia, 2003	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Calophyllaceae	AM (Amanã); BA (Sebastião Laranjeiras); ES (Linhares); GO (Pirenópolis); PE (Rio Preto); RN (Canguaretama); MG (São Tomé das Letras); MS (Corumbá, Santa Terezinha); RJ (Carapebus); SC (Babitonga); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Lopesia marginalis</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Chrysobalanaceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Casimiro de Abreu, Niterói); BA (Caravelas, Conde); ES (Alto Limoeiro, Itaguaçu, Itarana, Linhares, São Mateus.); RJ (Maricá (original description), Mangaratiba, Niterói, Cabo Frio; Carapebus, Casimiro de Abreu); AM (undetermined); MG (Diamantina, Jaboticatubas, Lagoa Santa, Santa Rita do Riacho.); PB (Caaporã);
<i>Lopesia maricaensis</i> Rodrigues & Maia, 2010	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Burseraceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães, original description)
<i>Lopesia mataybae</i> Garcia & Urso-Guimarães, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Sapindaceae	

<i>Lopesia mimosae</i> Maia, 2010	Caatinga	gall inducer	Fabaceae	PE (Parnamirim, original description)
<i>Lopesia pernambucensis</i> Maia, 2010	Caatinga	gall inducer	Fabaceae	PE (Parnamirim and Garanhuns, original description); BA (Ibiassucê)
<i>Lopesia pleromatis</i> Maia, 2022	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	SP (Bertioga, original description)
<i>Lopesia similis</i> Maia, 2004	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Burseraceae	AL (Maceió); BA (Conde, Porto Seguro); ES (Conceição da Barra); MG (Perdizes, Itamonte, São Tomé das Letras); MS (Aquidauana); MT (Cocalino); PA (Serra do Cachimbo, Ponta da Pedra); PB (João Pessoa); RJ (Carapebus (original description); Arraial do Cabo, Macaé, Quissamã, São João da Barra); SE (Itaporanga d' Ajuda)
<i>Lopesia simplex</i> Maia, 2002	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Burseraceae	RJ (Carapebus (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Macaé, Mangaratiba, Maricá, Quissamã, São João da Barra); ES (Guarapari, Vila Velha); MG (Belo Horizonte, Ouro Preto)
<i>Lopesia singularis</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, Grumari, Mangaratiba, Marambaia.); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Lopesia spinosa</i> Maia, 2004	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	MG (Tiradentes (original description), Delfinópolis); SP (Altinópolis, Jundiá)
<i>Lopesia tibouchinae</i> Maia, 2004	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	MG (Tiradentes (original description), Patrocínio); RJ (Santa Maria Madalena)
<i>Lopesia ubatubensis</i> Garcia & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	SP (Ubatuba, original description)
<i>Machaerobia gemmae</i> Maia, 2016	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Parque Nacional da Serra de Órgãos, original description)
<i>Machaerobia machaerii</i> (Kieffer, 1913i)	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	SC (Tubarão, original description); SP (Ribeirão Preto)

<i>Macroporpa peruviana</i> Rübsaamen, 1915a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	AC (Auristela, original description)
<i>Macroporpa ulei</i> Rübsaamen, 1915a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Lauraceae	AC (São Francisco, original description)
<i>Manilkaramyia notabilis</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	RJ (Carapebus); ES (Guarapari)
<i>Mayteniella distincta</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Celastraceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Cagarras, Carapebus, Copacabana, Grumari, Ilha das Folhas, Jacarepaguá, Macaé, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, São Francisco de Itabapoana, São João da Barra, Saquarema); ES (Guarapari, Presidente Kennedy); SC (Babitonga)
<i>Megaulus sterculiae</i> Rübsaamen, 1915a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Sterculiaceae	AC (São Francisco, original description)
<i>Metasphondylia squamosa</i> Tavares, 1918	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Malvaceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Meunieriella dalechampiae</i> Rübsaamen, 1905b	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	RJ (Palmeiras, original description)
<i>Meunieriella insignis</i> (Tavares, 1922)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Burseraceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Meunieriella lantanae</i> (Tavares, 1918a)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Meunieriella spinosa</i> Urso-Guimarães, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MG (Delfinópolis, original description)
<i>Mikaniadiplosis annulipes</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (, Rio de Janeiro (original description), Angra dos Reis); RS (Santa Tereza); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Mycodiplosis rubida</i> (Felt, 1911c)	NI	fungivorous	Pucciniales, Uredinales	Brazil (undetermined, original description)
<i>Myrciamyia maricaensis</i> Maia, 1996	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo Cabo Frio, Carapebus)
<i>Myrciamyia pterandrae</i> Maia & Flor, 2018	Cerrado	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	MG (Quartel São João, original description)

<i>Myrciariamyia admirabilis</i> Maia, 2007	Cerrado	gall inducer	Erythroxylaceae	MG (Tiradentes (original description), São Tomé das Letras); GO (Silvânia, Hidrolândia); SP (Ingaí)
<i>Myrciariamyia bivalva</i> Maia, 1995	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Carapebus)
<i>Myrciariamyia fernandesi</i> Maia, 2004	Cerrado	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	MG (Tiradentes, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera cerei</i> Rübsaamen, 1905	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Cactaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description); Angra dos Reis, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Mangaratiba, São João da Barra); ES (Conceição da Barra)
<i>Neolasioptera cupheae</i> Gagné, 1998	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Lythraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera eugeniae</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	ES (Conceição da Barra, Guarapari); RJ (Maricá (original description), Angra dos Reis, Araruama, Arraial do Cabo Cabo Frio, Grumari, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Parque Nacional do Itatiaia, Paraty, São João da Barra), Saquarema; MG (Itamonte)
<i>Neolasioptera fariae</i> Tavares, 1922	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	NI	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera ingae</i> Möhn, 1964	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Marambaia, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera lantanae</i> Tavares, 1922	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	BA (Salvador, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera pantaneira</i> Maia, 2017	Pantanal	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MS (Corumbá, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera ramicola</i> Maia, 2009	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Solanaceae	RS (Bento Gonçalves, original description)
<i>Neolasioptera urvilleae</i> (Tavares, 1909)	Pampa	gall inducer	Sapindaceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)
<i>Neomitranthella robusta</i> Maia, 1996c	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Saquarema)
<i>Novocalmonia fici</i> Ozdikmen, 2009	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Moraceae	BA (Itaparica, Santo Antonio da Barra)
<i>Novocalmonia urostigmatis</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Moraceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)

<i>Ouradiplosis aurata</i> Felt, 1915b	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Undetermined	PA (Igarapé-Açú, original description)
<i>Parametasphondylia piperis</i> Maia & Santos, 2007	Cerrado	gall inducer	Piperaceae	MG (Tiradentes, original description)
<i>Parazalepidota clusiae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Clusiaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Grumari, Mauá, Macaé, Petrópolis, São Gonçalo, Saquarema, Quissamã)
<i>Parkiamyia paraensis</i> Maia, 2006	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	PA (Oriximiná, original description)
<i>Paulliniamyia ampla</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapindaceae	RJ (Arraial do Cabo (original description), Araruama, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Maricá, São João da Barra, São Francisco de Itabapoana, Saquarema)
<i>Perasphondylia mikaniae</i> Gagné, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Silva Jardim (original description), Itatiaia, Paraty); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Perasphondylia reticulata</i> Möhn, 1960	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	PA (undetermined, original description)
<i>Pisphondylia brasiliensis</i> Couri & Maia, 1992	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo, São João da Barra; BA (Porto Seguro); ES (Santa Teresa; MG (Brumadinho); RS (Porto Alegre); SC (Babitonga, São Francisco do Sul); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Porricondyla pantaneira</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Pantanal	fungivorous	NA	MT (Poconé and Nova Mutum, original description)
<i>Porricondyla wenzeli</i> Garcia, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2023	Atlantic Forest	fungivorous	NA	AL (Quebrangulo, original description)
<i>Primadiplosis microgramma</i> Maia, 2011	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Polypodiaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)
<i>Proasphondylia brasiliensis</i> Felt, 1915	NI	gall inducer	NA	PE (Bonito, original description)
<i>Proasphondylia formosa</i> Maia, 1994	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)

<i>Proasphondylia guapirae</i> Maia, 1994	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Nyctaginaceae	RJ (Arraial do Cabo (original description), Angra dos Reis, Carapebus, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Maricá; ES (Santa Teresa); SC (Babitonga); SP (Bertioga)
<i>Procontarinia mangiferae</i> (Felt, 1911d)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Anacardiaceae	BA (Itaparica, Santo Antonio da Barra)
<i>Prodiplosis floricola</i> Felt, 1907b	NI	gall inducer	Ranunculaceae, Caryocaraceae, Rutaceae	SP (undetermined)
<i>Rhoasphondylia friburgensis</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	RJ (Nova Friburgo, original description)
<i>Rochadiplosis tibouchinae</i> Tavares, 1917	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Melastomataceae	RJ (Petrópolis, Nova Friburgo, and Tijuca, original description); SP (Altinópolis)
<i>Schismatodiplosis lantanae</i> (Rübsaamen, 1908)	Amazon Forest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Verbenaceae	SC (Tubarão, original description), RJ (Cabo Frio (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Casimiro de Abreu, Itatiaia, Mangaratiba, Maricá, Rio das Ostras, Rio das Ostras, São João da Barra, Saquarema, Valença); MG (Aimorés, Vale do Rio Doce); PA (Oriximiná)
<i>Schizomyia barreirensis</i> Santos, Maia & Calado, 2019	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	BA (Barreiras, original description)
<i>Schizomyia macrocapillata</i> Maia, 2005	Cerrado, Caatinga	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MG (Três Marias, original description); BA (Barreiras, Caetité); GO (Hidrolândia, Monte Alegre, Cavalcante); MT (Selvária)
<i>Schizomyia manihoti</i> Tavares, 1925	NI	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	CE (undetermined, original description)
<i>Schizomyia maricaensis</i> Sousa & Maia, 2007	Atlantic Forest, Cerrado	gall inducer	Malpighiaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description); SP (Ribeirão Preto)
<i>Schizomyia mimosae</i> Tavares, 1925	NI	gall inducer	Fabaceae	CE (undetermined, original description).
<i>Schizomyia santosi</i> Maia & Araújo, 2009	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Convolvulaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description)

<i>Schizomyia spherica</i> Maia & Oliveira, 2007	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo Carapebus,)
<i>Schizomyia tuiuiu</i> Urso-Guimarães & Amorim, 2002	Cerrado	gall inducer	Fabaceae	MT (Cuiabá, original description); SP (Ribeirão Preto)
<i>Smilasioptera candelariae</i> Möhn, 1975	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Smilacaceae	RJ (Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Carapebus, Grumari, Mangaratiba, Marambaia, Maricá, São João da Barra, Saquarema)
<i>Sphaeromyia flava</i> Maia, 2007	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Meliaceae	SP (Bertioga, original description); SC (São Francisco do Sul)
<i>Sphaerodiplosis dubia</i> Rübsaamen, 1915	NI	gall inducer	NI	Brazil (undetermined, original description)
<i>Stephomyia clavata</i> Tavares, 1920	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	BA (Madre de Deus, original description)
<i>Stephomyia epeugeniae</i> Gagné, 1994	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Stephomyia espiralis</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Mangaratiba)
<i>Stephomyia mina</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Carapebus)
<i>Stephomyia rotundifoliorum</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá, original description); ES (Conceição da Barra)
<i>Stephomyia tetralobae</i> Maia, 1993	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Myrtaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo)
<i>Stomatosema camilae</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Pantanal	fungivorous	NA	MS (Corumbá, original description)
<i>Stomatosema pantaneirum</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Pantanal, Cerrado	fungivorous	fungivorous	MS (Corumbá (original description), Bodoquena)
<i>Stomatosema paratudo</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Pantanal	fungivorous	fungivorous	MS (Corumbá, original description)

<i>Stomatosema sisbiota</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Pantanal, Cerrado	fungivorous	fungivorous	MS (Corumbá (original description), Bodoquena, Aquidauana)
<i>Stomatosema terena</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Cerrado	fungivorous	fungivorous	MS (Aquidauana, original description)
<i>Stomatosema terere</i> Carmo-Neto, Lamas & Urso-Guimarães, 2019	Cerrado	fungivorous	fungivorous	MS (Aquidauana, original description)
<i>Styraxdiplosis caetitensis</i> Tavares, 1915	Atlantic Forest, Caatinga	gall inducer	Styracaceae	BA (Caetité, original description)
<i>Styraxdiplosis cearensis</i> Tavares, 1925	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Euphorbiaceae	CE (undetermined, original description)
<i>Termitomastus leptoproctus</i> Silvestri, 1901	Cerrado	fungivorous	NA	MT (Cuiabá, original description)
<i>Trotteria quadridentata</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Arraial do Cabo)
<i>Uleella dalbergiae</i> Rübsaamen, 1908	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Fabaceae	RJ (Jacarepaguá/Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Uleia clusiae</i> Rübsaamen, 1905a	Amazon Forest	gall inducer	Clusiaceae	AM (Santa Clara and Bonfim on Juruá River, original description)
<i>Youngomyia matogrossensis</i> Proença & Maia, 2019	Cerrado	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	MT (Chapada dos Guimarães, original description)
<i>Youngomyia pouteriae</i> Maia, 2001	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Sapotaceae	RJ (Maricá (original description), Araruama, Arraial do Cabo, Cabo Frio, Grumari, Mangaratiba, São João da Barra, Saquarema)
<i>Zalepidota ituensis</i> (Tavares, 1917)	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Asteraceae	SP (Salto de Itu, original description)
<i>Zalepidota piperis</i> Rübsaamen, 1908	Atlantic Forest	gall inducer	Piperaceae	RJ (Tijuca/Rio de Janeiro, original description)
<i>Zalepidota tavaresi</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	Pampa	gall inducer	Piperaceae	RS (São Leopoldo, original description)